

THE IMPORTANCE OF COMPOSITION IN ARTISTIC FINISHING WORKS

Rustamov Axtam Muxtarovich

*Navoi State Pedagogical Institute, "Fine Arts and engineering graphics"
teacher of the Department*

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Annotation: *Composition – as an academic subject, such special disciplines as sculpture, architecture, graphics, pencil drawing, painting, art history are inextricably linked. In a pencil drawing and color drawing, the artist directly refers to the basics of composition, without knowing its rules, it is impossible to understand the essence of the composition, pencil drawing, color drawing.*

Keywords: *Compositional techniques, means of composition, everyday genre, monumental and decorative art, pedagogy, artistic graphics, frontal composition, horizontal composition, vertical composition, diagonal composition.*

“We mobilize all the forces and opportunities of our state and society in order for our young people to be able to independently think, have high intellectual and spiritual potential, to be able to mature and be happy in the world as people who do not come to their peers in any field.”

SH. M. Mirziyoev

The word composition is derived from Latin “compositio” – i.e. it means to compare the pieces of its subjects and place them in a certain order in a holistic way, to create according to an idea, to state, to compose a composition.

Composition is present on the basis of all types of art: literature, theater-cinema, music, fine and

applied art, architecture, etc. Composition appeared as a subject of study, after a pencil image, a color image, and now the composition course is included in the curriculum of higher education, specialized schools.

Pedagogy teaches students studying at the faculties of art studies of higher educational institutions the rules of composition, methods of expressing its elements in the correct form, along with the development of creative abilities in the science of composition. When creating a composition in the visual arts, a preamble is created by in-depth study of theoretical laws, such as shadow-light, color, air and line perspective, and the ability to skillfully apply them in visual activities. The composition course is of great importance in the development of figurative thinking in independent creative and pedagogical activity of students.

The science of composition consists of conversation, lectures and practical classes. The composition is perfectly studied by the Basic Rules of law, methods and means, students in the process of practical training and conversations.

Composition-as an educational subject, such specialist disciplines as haicality, architecture, graphics, pencil drawing, painting, art history are inextricably linked with each

other. In a pencil image and Color Image, The Artist directly refers to the basics of composition, without knowing its laws, he does not understand the essence of composition, pencil image, Color Image.

Artistic finishing works, like all types of Fine Art, are carried out based on the General Laws of the composition. That is why these works, while requiring sufficient knowledge and skills from the decorator artist, require constant attention to the issues of composition.

In artistic finishing works, there are types of composition: flat, volumetric, with width and depth. All this will have some kind of general quality and character in the implementation of this or that idea.

Frontal composition means the organization of a frontal image by two coordinates. A characteristic feature of the Frontal composition is the limitation of the use of volumetric elements in it and, at the same time, an increase in the possibilities of enlarging its measurements. Therefore, even if some relief images (for example: candelabra, wood and ganch carvings and hacksaws) are built on the laws of plastic, a flat surface belongs to the type of compositions.

Most of the decorative work in educational institutions, for example, visual aids, wall publications,

thematic pannos, invitations, greeting cards, thematic Al'bom, etc., is performed on the basis of frontal composition. The construction of the composition will depend on the function and content of the particular object, the purpose for which it is intended. The main structures of the compositions are as follows:

horizontal composition-in this case, the elements of the composition are placed on a horizontal surface. For example: Field, city panorama, etc.

Vertical composition is an active, dynamic composition that creates the illusion of upward growth, flight, the details of which are located mainly on a steep line.

Diagonal composition – its construction is based on dynamic and intense schemes.

A triangular or pyramidal composition – in this case, a stable, calm state is relied on. The lower part of the surface of the photo is the base of the pyramid.

One of the important features of Frontal compositions is their performance in the form of a thin surface. Frontal composition differs from other types of compositions in that it gives volume, distance and width.

Volumetric composition – comes in the form of a three-stroke

unit, designed for perception from different viewing points.

In accordance with the content and task of the works, some feature of the composition can be exaggerated. The composition, with its properties, ultimately serves as the basis for ensuring the High Artistry of artistic finishing works. In the harmonic integrity of the compositions, colors also acquire special significance. Especially the mosaic banner, in which color occupies the main place, should be taken seriously to the composite harmony in stained glass windows. Only then will the color unity of the work be one of the most basic factors affecting aesthetics. Unreasonable deviation from the laws of composition usually reduces both the content and aesthetic nature of artistic finishing works.

If the elements of the composition are located in the same way in relation to each other on the sides, they will be in compositional balance. One of the main issues of composition is combination. On the basis of the combination, New Expressive variants of the composition are prepared by changing the location of one and several elements. Movement and stagnant compositions also have their own laws. Between these, it is necessary not to allow the origin of the opposite meaning, that is, to

achieve the logical harmony of the main and secondary elements. Knowledge of the laws of rhythm will greatly help to correctly choose the character of a rhythmic look when composing an impressive composition.

Artists are charged with such responsibilities as enriching the means of creating artistic images in their works, expanding the scale of their worldview with the experiences of advanced artists of the civilized world.

Indeed, today international life, the development of personality have entered such a stage in which advanced technologies, not military power, but intellectual potential, intelligence, thought, are of decisive importance. Now, any state, any nation is strong, first of all, with its high culture and spirituality.

The future of our country directly depends on the training of unconditional personnel. In order to educate a harmonious generation with a new thinking, modern knowledge, to have an organizer and resourceful staff, it is necessary to radically change the educational system, raise it to the level of demand of the period, become one of the most important tasks of our society, each of us.

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